

[Belge başlığını yazın]

Uma Shankar Yadav

2022

OPEN ACCESS

Volume II, Issue 3

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***MSME INDUSTRIES IN UTTAR
PRADESH WITH SPECIAL FOCUS
ON (ODOP) ALIGARH LOCK IN-
DUSTRY AND MOONJ CRAFT OF
PRAYAGRAJ.***

Bank and Policy

ISSN: 2790-1041

E-ISSN: 2790-2366

www.bankandpolicy.org

zenodo

Citation: Uma Shankar Yadav¹, Ravindra Tripathi, Mano Ashish Tripathi, Nasir Mammadov (2022) MSME industries in Uttar Pradesh with special focus on (ODOP) Aligarh lock industry and Moonj craft of Prayagraj. *Bank and Policy*, 2(3): 17-29
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6508308

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Received: MAR 25, 2022

Accepted: APR 30, 2022

ABSTRACT:

The SME sector is one of the most important sectors in India. In recent years, the micro, small, and medium-sized sectors have emerged as a competitive and vibrant sector of the Indian economy, showing exceptional growth in production, jobs, and distributed development in general and exports in particular. Handicraft products are generally sustainable products made by hand or with the help of simple tools that are self-made by hand in the whole process artisan that made the craft product is called craftsmen and they use natural resources like as wood, claystone, bamboo, jute, moonj, willow plant, banana leaf, monas plant, some special shrubs, and scrub found in a forest or simply forest material some special stone also occur in river ocean, and like sheep, and the product is made by these handicraft artisans so this sector is also called sustainable industry now days. India is called for it its natural product hasta la so-called the land of handicraft products in the world The current paper talks about the importance of the SME sector in India.

Keywords: SME, Small Business, Competitive Advantage of India, lock industry global handicraft index.

Introduction

Micro, small and medium-sized enterprises play a dominant position in both developed and developing countries' economic growth, cottage and small-scale industries play important role in creating employment opportunities, equitable distribution of national income, balanced regional growth, and development of rural and semi-urban areas. This sector, in particular in developing countries such as India, is considered to be a driver of growth because of its contribution to income generation, jobs, and GDP.

Micro, small and medium-sized companies are demonstrating their effect on national and regional economies worldwide. They have been recognized as an important tool for generating job opportunities with a limited amount of capital expenditure in both developed and developing countries.

Small-scale and cottage industries also play an important role in reducing regional disparities. Only the rapid growth and promotion of small-scale manufacturing in a backward area will achieve industrial development Burra (1987). India's SME sector is a central element in

its economic growth history (Yadav et al 2022a). The industry has the potential to spread economic development throughout the nation and can be a major partner in helping to accelerate the process of inclusive growth by employing, in addition to the agricultural sector, 40 percent of the country's workforce Jain (2003); Lelyveld (1978). The model of the socio-economic policies of the Government of India has always been tiny, small, and medium-sized companies Louis (2008).

This sector plays a vital role in growing and developing the Indian economy. Moreover, this improvement needs to be sustained as it contributes substantial revenues to the central exchequer Mann (1992).

A large share of industrial production, job creation, and GDP contributions is also accounted for by MSMEs Malika (2005). Therefore, it is understood that MSMEs play a crucial role in the development of the country.

Definition of MSME Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises

Micro units

MSMEs will now be called Micro units if they have investments up to Rs 1 crore and a turnover of less than Rs 5 crore. The definition earlier was on investment criteria of up to Rs 10 lakh for Service MSMEs and Rs 25 lakh for manufacturing Murtahin (1995); Nayak (1994).

Small units

For an MSME to be defined as a Small unit, its investment limit has been raised from Rs 5 crore to Rs 10 crore with a turnover of fewer than 50 crores Nevill (1926). This applies to all MSMEs.

Medium units

Enterprises with investments up to Rs 20 crore with a turnover of less than Rs 100 crore will now be called Medium units. Earlier, the investment limit for Medium units was up to Rs 10 crore and for Service enterprises up to

Existing and Revised Definition of MSMEs

Existing MSME Classification			
Criteria : Investment in Plant & Machinery or Equipment			
Classification	Micro	Small	Medium
Mfg. Enterprises	Investment < Rs. 25 lac	Investment < Rs. 5 cr.	Investment < Rs. 10 cr.
Services Enterprise	Investment < Rs. 10 lac	Investment < Rs. 2 cr.	Investment < Rs. 5 cr.
Revised MSME Classification			
Composite Criteria : Investment And Annual Turnover			
Classification	Micro	Small	Medium
Manufacturing & Services	Investment < Rs. 1 cr. and Turnover < Rs.5 cr.	Investment < Rs. 10 cr. and Turnover < Rs.50 cr.	Investment < Rs. 20 cr. and Turnover < Rs.100 cr.

FIGURE 1
MICRO SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES

Source: Ministry of MSME.

Rs 5 crore Figure 1.

Figure1: Micro Small and Medium Enterprises.

Source: Ministry of MSME.

A new classification of MSME 2020 from the ministry of MSME

The classification of MSME for both goods and services organizations are done based on the turnover and are as follows: - for this follow table 1 below.

Classification	Turnover
Micro-Enterprise	Up to Rs. 5 Crores
Small Enterprise	Rs. 5 Crores to Rs. 75 Crores
Medium Enterprise	Rs. 75 Crores to Rs. 250 Crores

Until recently, the classification of MSMEs was done based on the investment put in the business. It was calculated as a total of the money invested in the plant, machinery, and equipment.

For a company manufacturing goods-Micro Enterprise- up to Rs. 25 lakhs

Small Enterprise- Rs. 25 lakhs – 5 crores

Medium Enterprise- Rs. 5 crores – 10 crores

For a service organization-

Micro Enterprise- up to Rs. 10 lakhs

Small Enterprise- up to Rs. 10 lakhs – 2 crores

Medium Enterprise- Rs. 2 crores – 5 crores

Due to this classification, the government had to incur expenses to physically verify the actual assets and chart up the actual investments made. Now, the government has passed a new bill, which classifies the MSMEs based on their annual turnover instead of investment. The revised basis for the classification of MSMEs based on turnover has made it easier for both the government and the industries to recog-

nize a business as an MSME. The Government can look up the GST database to match the actual turnover cited by an organization and accordingly classify it into the MSME category. Unlike the previous classification basis where the criteria were different for goods and service sectors, in the revised parameters there is just one basis of classification for goods and service sectors (GOI MSME 2020).

Aligarh lock industries introduction

Aligarh is an important business center of Uttar Pradesh and it is well known as the city of locks in India. Due to the ease of availability of the raw materials and power supply, Aligarh has emerged as a good business centre. Aligarh locks are exported across the world.

In 1890, local entrepreneurs initiated the production of locks on a small scale here. Today, the city holds thousands of manufacturers, exporters, and suppliers involved in the brass, bronze, iron, and aluminium industries (Yadav et al 2022 and India mart). The different processes of lock-making are carried out in different units. Aligarh has several popular landmarks. A few of them are Aligarh fort, Khereshwar Temple, Teerthdham Mangalayatan Mandir, etc.

Locks and Hardware

The locks manufactured in Aligarh are immensely popular all over the country. Padlocks, door locks, multi-slot, bicycle locks, multi-purpose locks, etc. are produced in the district. Locks and hardware production is the cottage industry here. See figures 2 and 3 below for lock and key works in Aligarh.

Figure 3 (3). Lock making works in Aligarh photo taken from (India, MAR 2021)

Role of SME

In the global economy, micro, small and medium-sized enterprises play a crucial role, and they are considered the engine of growth in most countries (Yadav et al 2022b). MSMEs ensure a more equal distribution of national income, fuel balanced regional industrial growth, serve as a nursery for entrepreneurship, and promote the mobilization of local capital and otherwise unused skills (Yadav et al 2021).

They also play a key role in developing the economy with their strong, profitable, scalable, and innovative entrepreneurial spirit. Today, the small-scale industry is called Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises, based on their investment. Compared to medium and large-scale industries, small industries are small in operational employment, products, energy, technology, etc (Yadav et al 2022c).

The micro, small, and medium-sized sectors have emerged in recent years as a dynamic and vibrant sector of the Indian economy, with exceptional growth in the production, employment, and distributed growth sectors in general and in exports in particular. Consequently, the Government of India has encouraged and supported the promotion of small-scale industries through explicit policies such as protection against large-scale industry, capital subsidies, differential tax treatment, reservation, etc (Yadav et al 2020).

The objective of the study

- To study the small industry in India with special reference to the lock industry of Aligarh.
- To suggest strategies and approaches for developing a global handicraft index

Review of the literature

Khadi and Handloom, Handicraft, Village Industries, Bamboo Based Industries, Sericulture, and Lock, etc. are traditional small-scale industries GoI (2006). A wide range of products ranging from relatively simple items to sophisticated products such as television sets, electronic control systems, mixer grinders, and various engineering products are produced by modern small-scale industries, particularly as ancillary to large industries GoUP (1981). Traditional small businesses are highly labor-intensive, whereas modern small-scale units use highly advanced machinery and equipment Hasnain (2007). The following literature supports the current study, like the study done by Yadav U.S et al 2020 described the important steps that are useful for the development of this sector of the country they explained the import of hand-made carpet and shazar stores. (Vanita ahlat 2018) Her paper focused on labor

productivity and countries' textile sector" she has discussed in her paper that most of the laborers are women in the textile industry. A study conducted by Roy, Patnaik, and Satpathy (2020) for 690 handicraft industries (Small business) enterprises found a drastic fall in the growth rate (this was due to pandemic Covid -19 of net sales by (-)66.7% in the first quarter of the financial year 2020–21. Yadav U.S et al 2022 discussed a visionary concept of the global handicraft index and role of the role of handicraft artisan and strategies for the development of the. The situation worsened further when the government announced the extended nationwide lockdown amidst the COVID-19 crisis. Ananda, Abhishek, et. al (2020) and (Yadav et al 2022). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)." Results suggested that there is enormous gender disparity in employment; that is women are very few in comparison to men workers. published their research paper "Study of Handicraft Marketing Strategies of Artisans in Uttar Pradesh and Its Implications" as we have discussed the performance of the handicraft sector and the role of women in the handicraft sector or home-based industry. But (Yadav et al 2022) published about the performance of women in ODOP of Uttar Pradesh and they gave an initial approach to the developing global handicraft index for small businesses. A new concept for the development of the handicraft industry in the world and to enhance the positive completion in a new era there is a need for a global handicraft index (Yadav et al 2022b) and (Yadav et al 2021). We know that women are involved in the handicrafts sector and their performance is increasing day by day even during the pandemic time. So it needs to make strategies for its development in the handicraft industry Yadav et al 2022a). in the case of formal and infor-

mal knowledge transformation in the hand-made carpet industry, Yadav et al analyzed the good criteria for the transformation of institutions, (Yadav et al 2022). How to develop business strategies for upgrading the handicraft artisan's skills there is a need for special strategies (Yadav et al 2021). (Yadav Nassir Mammadove et al 2022d) described important small industries in Azerbaijan and different handicraft industries and how to develop special strategies in the sector. some famous handicrafts industries in Uttar Pradesh are also in the decline phase and we need to improve this shazar stone sector (Yadav et al 2022)

Prayagraj Moonj craft a family-based business during lockdown

During pandemic time when people were not touching any bag basket from the market or no politeness due afraid of corona infection then Moonj craft made product were in daily use of rural urban and tribal people of india this is green eco-friendly biodegradable easily available moonj craft in following district of Uttar Pradesh and it helped family income generation and most the women engaged in the making of Moonj craft because of lockdown they spent their time in making Dalia basket bag carry bag a etc. product and safe from outer infection of disease and this created a new entrepreneur root for women and helped in earning money so now we try to understand about Moonj craft industry and role of this industry in family business and what was impact of pandemic on Mooj industry and how the solved their problem during this time so as we know that Moonj craft is famous craft of Allahabad Amethi Sultanpur district Allahabad handicraft called Moonj craft in local there are several product of Moonj craft named basket like as Dalia, dauri, bhauki, sika, in north yeast language and the raw material naturally grow in per-

ennial grass called Sarpat and kusha in vilage and in local language this plant is grow in lowland of the district in Prayagraj, Amethi, Jaunpur, but mostly famous in Allahabad and Amethi district local at the bank of small river like Mansaita river in phoolpur tehsil and phaphamau block Baratar and katiyahi moonj (Moonj craft village of Uttar Pradesh)at the bank of Yamuna (yadav et al 2021b) .

Near about 1500 women is painstaking cut soaked color and weave the kasha grass with a combination of the Carpet or Sarkanda Grass that is used for binding the kasha grass and giving a shape according to artisan to craft magic and form Moonj craft with or without lids or a range they make bread baskets and laundry and keep shake baskets and they make all the tableware mat cot round and square fruit basket for the table and shopping basket for shopping and is eco-friendly sustainable fully biodegradable this is a green product in free in a variety Brilliant Colors, Textures, And Style(Jadhav s,2020).

Agricultural uses

We found during a field survey found that 24 wild species of below like plant that was used in support agricultural activity mostly carpet, tutor but also provide shelter from winter frost and different utility and decorative handmade products are made by this agricultural palate sometimes called twins grant holder, and sovescio (green manure). Parada M, Selga A, Bonet at al 2007.

The result has been found in many shrubs-like plant species that were used to fixing of cultivated plants to tutor. For example, in the cultivation and plantation of willow plants in the winter season the fruit-bearing shoots of white color are planted edge of the land and in srub like a forest, they are a long thin, and particularly flexible

parent (Chiovenda-Bensi et al 2000) several plant species are being employed in the production and occupation related to sheep rearing and paneer making and they mostly scrub typical color and for goat and sheep bells of best craft artisanship are created from Acer carpet wood plant and the banana plantains an agricultural handicraft in the Uttar Pradesh.

Bamboo and its craft

Before the description, bamboo agriculture and handicrafts explain bamboo placement and coasters, bamboo clothing, and other bamboo fabrics. bamboo toys bamboo fabrics and furniture, bamboo winds chimes, bamboo birdfeeders and nesting boxes bamboo lanterns, and lamps, bamboo is cultivated in many countries like China, Myanmar Thailand, Bhutan, and different handicraft product are made with bamboo and can be crafted if we see the example of bamboo craft like as ca, bamboo sculpture, bamboo bag, bamboo paper basket, etc. are the product of bamboo.in India Nagaland, Tripura Assam, and Uttar Pradesh is big produce bamboo grass their product is decorative utility purposes, and big demand in foreign like Europe, America, Africa continent. China is the also larger produce of bamboo grass and produces cotton and silk for manikin purpose Cotton and Silk (Rituagrahari 2017).

if we discuss the cotton craft then many cotton sarees and silk sari are made by cotton and some insect are brought upon Mulberry plant called the silkworm, and by the help of cocoon this silk is produced it contains hot water boil and upper layer form fine yarn like structure and .tsars, moonga, Ire, silk is famous in the world market China and India are big producers of silk and many handicraft products are made by silk and cotton .cotton cultivation in China and India, Bangladesh is a major country and

much handmade product and textile industry is dependent on this product (Anand et. al(2020).

And its practical use in agriculture fields and is what many craftsmen used woods grass and grass products for many centuries ago, but that agricultural products have been proven to be flexible and strongest in tensile than the steel, and much flexible and much resistant against many disease infestation, thus we can say the tools as much ha a crop some crucial crop use are vegetable stakes bean pole trellis pole shade lathe irrigation pipes and lathe ditch lining, fencing the make bamboo invaluable technology for peasant but as a crop of banana, jute, cotton, bamboo is a much profitable as products made from jute cotton and bamboo uses and important bamboo and can be made crops. These crops may be grown for any reason, depending on the intended and special finished product as the utilization of bamboo. there are different crops grown for different purposes decoration, plant matter, gardens, landscaping, intermediate product, and raw materials food items bamboos, musical instrument construction and furniture material flutes drums, roofing tiles saxophone. chairs tables, sofas, armories, pictures, decorative wall hanging weapons bed frames, curtains, jewelry, different conservation of bamboo carps to lesion soil, and desertification it is an important part of agriculture and versatile part, whether it is cultivated to be a tool that utilized in the growth of other crops and offers many options to non-renewable and hardwood and softwood materials (Yadav et al 2021 bank and policy).

Aligarh Lock Industry

Aligarh is located approximately 90 miles (140 km) southeast of the capital city of New Delhi. Aligarh is an important business center and is most famous for its lock in-

dustry. Aligarh is popularly known as the "Tala Nagri" of India. In Aligarh, there are both small and medium units in the lock industry. The city is famous for its Rs4000 crore lock industry. Hundreds of miles away in Aligarh, around 5 sq kilometers there is an area from Upper Court to Gonda road where workers and owners of small units are engaged in the lock making mostly from the Muslim community (Nayak p 1994). According to the latest records shared by District Industries Centre, there are about 5,000 registered lock-manufacturing units in Aligarh. Some of the large players in the Lock Industry are Edwin Brown Hardware Company, Allen and Alwan Locks, and Link Locks. The company manufactures many items like Solid Brass Hardware including Door, Window, and Cabinet fitting, Black Iron, Numerals, Fireplace Furnishing, Curtain Hardware in Brass, Aluminium, Copper, Steel Bronze, and Zinc.

Taking about the history of the lock industry, the lock industry in Aligarh was established nearly 130 years ago when a company named Johnson and Co. started importing locks from England to sell them in Aligarh. Then thousands of manufacturers, exporters, and suppliers became involved in the locks of brass, bronze, iron, and aluminium.

Aligarh locks are exported across the world in counties USA, U.K, Europe, Middle East, Africa, etc. Apart from locks, Aligarh is also famous for brass hardware and sculptures. Eighty percent of Muslims are engaged in the lock industry and are experts in making a variety of locks. There are over 10,000 units in the industry including micro and small firms. The industry earns nearly Rs. 4000 crores as annual turnover. The industry exports its products to various countries like Europe, parts of Asia, the USA, Australia, Africa, and the UK. Some of the big players in the lock industry export

goods outside India but the small units usually sell within India.

Another important factor why some lock industries excel is because of a concept known as learning by doing. A learning curve is defined as a curve relating unit costs to accumulated volume, which affects future costs and market position

Challenges faced by Aligarh lock Industry

Aligarh lock industry is facing many challenges and is struggling hard for survival. Availability of major raw materials used to make locks such as zinc, brass, copper, etc. also plays a vital role in sustaining this lock industry Satyajit (2012); Sharma (2005).

The lock manufacturing industry especially small enterprises in the district of Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh, is facing several problems These challenges are posing as hurdles in the growth of the lock industry, and hamper the smooth flow of work of some of the units. Some of the problems faced by the Aligarh Lock industry in recent years are:

h which was announced by the government as Tala NagThe government meant made available to businessmen plots for the industrial purpose at low rates but later the government, from a different ruling party sold the plots at a very high rate as if it were real estate business. Even the National Small Scale Industries Corporation, which was established to promote the business of locks in Aligarh, did not add too much value to this industry's development.

Competition from Chinese Lock

Currently, the Indian lock market is majorly flooded with Chinese locks imports which have majorly affected small and medium scale enterprise manufacturing locks

in Aligarh. According to the latest estimates, only 20 percent of the Indian market is served by Indian manufacturers, with the rest being accounted for by imports mainly from China and Italy.

The primary cottage, tiny lock factories here not only have to deal with a lack of necessities like the power they are also being squeezed out of the market by the flood of cheap Chinese locks. Chinese industry price-wise is very competitive and no one in the world, including India, can compete with them in prices.

Conclusion

Thus we see the famous Moon craft in Allahabad is included in the ODOP program which was launched by the UP government in 2018 and the second industry is famous in the world for its special lock industry of Aligarh is posing a very serious problem in recent years. Moon is a decorative, sustainable, and green product and has religious value in Hindu dharma. It is the negligence of state or price competitiveness and direct competition from the Chinese locks which has brought this industry to its downfall (Radhkrishnan, P. (2009). Some of the big industry players say that Chinese locks are no threat to us because Chinese products are high on aesthetics and finish whereas security needs durability and reliability, which Aligarh lock provides. They also claim that the UP government provides them subsidized raw materials, relaxation in taxes, better infrastructure like a supply of power, and a smooth transportation system, which can throw Chinese threats out of the window (Satyajit Majumdar, Nia, C. (2012).

The next generation of families which are engaged in the lock-making industry is sending their children from higher studies abroad so that they learn about new technology to make locks and manage the in-

dustry. Moreover, they are giving special training programs to laborers to manufacture locks. Government should start a testing center in Aligarh and a training center at Aligarh to ensure that better quality locks are produced and to motivate youngsters to join the industry (Hussain m 2006)

One way to bring about a boom in the industry is to design locks highlighting their security value. This will also save it from closure. When there is development and profit in the industry, there are still some points that need to be paid heed to, especially when it comes to the aid of the government. For the last few years, there has been a crisis in the hardware industry and this is due to the illegal copying of designs and selling things without bills. The right and smooth implementation of the schemes and policies of the government alone can bring about a lot of reform in the industry. Though time-taking, this is the best solution for the industry to prosper (Louies p 2007).

The lock manufacturers of Aligarh have also been demanding the development of a Special Economic Zone (SEZ) for them in the town but despite the project being theoretically approved by the Union Commerce Ministry, it has hardly made any headway. The ministry has blamed the Uttar Pradesh government for delaying the landmarking and acquisition process (Yadav et al 2021b).

The famous lock industry of Aligarh, encompassing nearly one and a half-century of long history, is struggling hard to compete with international players in the era of today's globalization. As a result, its exports are almost nil. The small industrialists associated with the lock industry in Aligarh are finding it hard to make a living. The industry, which has always provided a secure guarantee, now finds itself in the edifice of insecurity. Small scale sector of India contributes 33% of India's export, but the Ali-

garh lock industry cuts a sorry figure in exporting their products range. Even in the local market also, 6 to 7% of locks are coming from China, which is a serious concern for Aligarh Lock Industries (Jain 2003 and GOI 2006)).

In 2001 the UN Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) and the Indian Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises agreed to implement a national program for the development of the Indian lock industry. Its objectives were technological upgrading to international levels, establishing distribution channels and market intelligence for product design, including the introduction of electronics and information technology in

design, training the workforce, and mechanization of processes (see <http://dcmsme.gov.in/emerge/npdli.htm>). Another objective was the development of a marketing network by participating in international and national fairs and conducting vendor development programs. However, the program has not yet been implemented (Yadav et al 2022). The lock industry needs support from the government for survival. Still, the dilemma is whether the situation of the Aligarh lock Industry will change? Let us hope the Government does what is expected out of it and wakes up soon to save the sinking ship of the Aligarh lock Industry (Burra et al 1987).

References

1. Burra, N. (1987). The exploitation of child workers in the lock industry of Aligarh. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 1117-1121.
2. Chattopadhyay, K., (1980) India's craft tradition, publication division Government of India
3. Gitanjali Goswami and Nivedita Goswami 2021 Impact of Covid-19 on the Traditional Handicrafts of Assam: A Study of Japi Making Craft journal of rural development <http://dx.doi.org/10.25175/jrd%2F2021%2Fv40%2Fi1%2F166502>
4. GoI (2020). Index of Industrial Production, Monthly, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation. Government of India
5. GoI (Various years). Annual Reports of the Ministry, DC MSME, Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, Government of India.
6. GoI, Government of India. (2006). Social, Economic and Educational Status of the Muslim community of India, A Report, Prime Minister's High-Level Committee Cabinet Secretariat. New Delhi, Sardar Patel Bhawan.
7. Group, Government of Uttar Pradesh. (1981). Uttar Pradesh District Gazetteer: Aligarh. Lucknow: Department of District Gazetteer Uttar Pradesh.
8. Hasnain, N. (2007). "Muslims in India: Caste Affinity and Social Boundaries of Backwardness". pp. 32-45 in *Basic Problems of OBC and Dalit Muslims*, edited by Ashfaq Husain Ansari. New Delhi: Serials Publications. <http://globalsociology.edublogs.org>
9. Jadhav, S., (2020) Indian Handicrafts: An overview of Growing or Depleting? *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*
9. JafariSadeghi,V., Dutta,D.K., Ferraris,A. & DeGiudice, M. (2020).Internationalization business processes in under-supported policy evidence from Italian SMEs. *Business Process Management Journal*, 26(5), 1055-1074.
10. Jain, P. (2003). "Locked Out".*Times of India*, Lucknow, 3rd June. Retrieved August 19, 2009

11. Kaviani, M.A., Tavana, M., Kowsari, F., And Rezapour, R. (2020). Supply chain resilience: a benchmarking model for vulnerability and capability assessment in the automotive industry. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 27(6), 1929-1949.
12. Khan, W.A, and Amir, Z. (2013) Study of Handicraft Marketing Strategies of Artisans in Uttar Pradesh and Its Implications. *Research Journal of Management Sciences*, 2(2)
13. Khurana, S., Haleem, A., Luthra, S., Huisingh, D., & Mannan, B. (2021). Now is the time to press the reset button: Helping India's companies to become more resilient and effective in overcoming the impacts of COVID-19, climate changes, and other crises. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 280(2), 124466.
14. Lelyveld, D. (1978). *Aligarh's First Generation: Muslim Solidarity in British India*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
15. Louis, P. (2008). "Social Exclusion: A Conceptual and Theoretical Framework." Retrieved March 15, 2009
16. Malika. B. (2005). Muslims in India: A Demographic and Socio-Economic Profile. *Journal of Muslim Minority Affairs*, 25(3).
17. Mann, E.A. (1992). *Boundaries and Identities: Muslims, Work, and Status in Aligarh*. New Delhi: Sage Publications India Pvt. Ltd. Mistry
18. Mano Ashish Tripathi, Ravindra Tripathi, Uma Shankar Yadav. The Gig Economy: Workers, Work, and Platform Perspective, *Journal of positive school psychology* 26(2): 3434 to 3450
19. Mathew, P.M., (2011). *Employment in Handloom and Handicrafts Sectors, Yojana*,
20. Mohi-us-din, Mir., (2014) A Study of the Impact of Government Policies on Marketing Strategy of Handicrafts. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* 5(2)
21. Murtahin, B.J.F. (1995). *Hindu Chauvinism and Muslims in India* Retrieved March 05, 2009.
22. Nayak, P. (1994). 'Economic Development and Social Exclusion in India', International Institute for Labor Studies (IILS). (Discussion Paper). (Retrieved December 20, 2009
23. Nevill, H.R. (1926). *Aligarh: A Gazetteer, Being Volume VI of the District Gazetteers of the United Provinces of Agra and Oudh*. Government Branch Press: Lucknow.
24. Radhkrishnan, P. (2009). "Globalization and Exclusion: The Indian Context." *Journal of the East Asia Foundation*, 4 (1). Retrieved September 10, 2009.
25. SatyajitMajumdar, Nia, C. (2012) "Cluster dynamics and performance in traditional industries: a critical review of lock, brassware and glassware industries in north India" in *Prospects of Regional Economic Cooperation in South Asia*.
26. Sharma, M., & Sharma, H., & Naqvi, F. (2005). Survival of Aligarh Lock Manufacturing Industry. *Economic and Political Weekly*. 40. 24-30.
27. Yadav U.S, Tripathi, R, Tripathi M.A Global handicraft index: a pioneering approach and developing strategies for promotion completion and Welfare of Artisan in the Digital World. *Bank and Policy*. 2022 DOI: 10.29228/imcra.18
28. Yadav U.s, Tripathi, R, Tripathi M.A 2020 (Strategies for development of handicraft sector small industries' in India)small enterprises development management and extension journal Sage publication September 2020

29. Yadav Uma Shankar, Nassir Mammadov, Ravindra Tripathi (2022) Small industries (Handicraft Sector) of Azerbaijan and impact of Pandemic-19 on Traditional craft: Strategies for Development of Handicraft Sector in Azerbaijan. *Bank and Policy*, 2(2): 112-127.
30. Yadav Uma Shankar, Tripathi R. India's toy industries and markets competition with global toys: An overview of the toy industry and how the sector is gearing up for an Aatmanirbhar Bharat. *Bank and Policy* 2(2): 86 -110.
31. Yadav Uma Shankar, Tripathi Ravindra, Tripathi mano Ashish, Gyan Prakash Yadav (2022). Indian small industries (Terracotta of Gorakhpur and Bankura) and women artisan in the digital and covid-19 era: a case study on the traditional handicraft in Uttar. *International Journal of Economy and Innovation*, Volume 22(2): 359 -370.
32. Yadav, U. S., Tripathi, R., Yadav, G. P., & Tripathi, M. A. (2022). Proposal of a Global Handicraft Index for Sustainable Development: A Visionary Approach for Small Industry and Developing Strategies for Handicraft (Rural Industry). *European Journal of Sustainable Development Research*, 6(2), DOI:10.21601/ejosdr/11909
33. Yadav, U. Shankar Yadav, Ravindra Tripathi, Mano Ashish Tripathi, Rajesh Kumar Shastri, Gyan Prakash Yadav, & Aliza. (2022). Entrepreneurial Development of Artisan in ODOP in Uttar Pradesh to Boost Economy: Strategies and New Approaches Towards Global Handicraft Index for Socio-Economic Welfare of Artisans. *Asian Journal of Management, Entrepreneurship, and Social Science*, 2(01), 1-17.
34. Yadav, U. Shankar Yadav, Ravindra Tripathi, Mano Ashish Tripathi, Rajesh Kumar Shastri, Gyan Prakash Yadav, & Aliza. (2022) Role of One district one product (ODOP) and Moonz craft of Uttar Pradesh: Strategies and new approaches for developing first Global Handicraft Index. *Bank and Policy* 1(1).
35. Yadav, U.S, Tripathi, R., Tripathi, M.A., Rawat, R., & Kushwaha, J. (2022). Performance of women artisans as entrepreneurs in odor in Uttar Pradesh to boost economy: strategies and away towards global handicraft index for small business. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 26(1), 1-19.
36. Yadav. U.S, Tripathi, R, Tripathi M.A. (2022). Exclusive and Digital analysis of the transformation of Institutions in the knowledge and innovation system of the hand-made world carpet industry. *Journal of positive school psychology*, 6(3):1135-1160